
Optimization of Resilient, Reliable, and Renewable Energy Infrastructure for Large-Scale Essential Services in Urban Environments

Final Report

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Executive Summary

Resilient, reliable, and renewable energy infrastructure is essential for critical applications such as data centers, hospitals, and military facilities, which demand strict energy service uptime despite the challenges of urban space constraints and the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources like solar and wind. Moreso, outages extending beyond a few hours reduce quality of life in ways that spur affected residents to pursue back-up generation.

Solutions for increasing resiliency include 1) hardening energy infrastructure, 2) developing distributed generation, and 3) increasing demand response capabilities. Hardening energy infrastructure, in many cases, includes expanding and undergrounding energy transmission systems, both of which are expensive processes. Likewise, developing distributed generation based on solar and battery energy storage is difficult due to solar capacity size constraints based on building rooftop area coupled with the high expense backup battery energy systems that are rarely utilized in order to ensure reliability. An alternate solution could be to utilize existing the gas transmission system coupled with distributed generation to increase the capacity of locally sited fuel cells. This approach has potential because the existing natural gas transmission infrastructure is substantially more reliable than the electric transmission system. Additionally, introducing renewable hydrogen into the gas transmission system would reduce and eliminate carbon emissions associated with gas pipeline operation, resulting in carbon neutral backup generation.

This work aims to demonstrate that renewable hydrogen, integrated with affordable, renewable grid power, offers a robust solution to achieve 100% renewable energy goals while meeting stringent reliability and resiliency standards. Through comprehensive modeling of Southern California's electrical and gas networks, this effort analyzes the dynamic interaction of hydrogen systems—including fuel cells, electrolyzers, and batteries—with local and remote renewable energy sources, the electric grid, and gas networks to address grid outages and improve energy system resilience. This report focuses on how the existing gas transmission system can firm up electricity supply in the face of a less resilient and reliable electric transmission system. Resiliency is examined from two perspectives: 1) when meeting the entire Southern California electrical load, and 2) when meeting a reduced Southern California electrical load based on critical loads from a societal and individual resident level. Subsequent work will reduce loads further, focusing on societal critical loads only (hospitals, communication, transportation, health and safety, water, and other critical infrastructure/loads).

The resiliency events considered in this work focus on examining the disabling of major electrical transmission lines that power Southern California. The main motivation for considering these transmission lines are public safety power shutoff (PSPS) events, and wild fires. A far less likely cause is equipment failure unrelated to PSPS and wildfire events. Gas transmission outages are not considered in this work because the gas transmission system has historically achieved resiliency and reliability metrics that are orders of magnitude better than electric transmission systems.

This work makes a key assumption that the gas transmission has been converted from carrying natural gas to hydrogen. Prior work has shown that the current natural gas transmission has sufficient capacity to power gas power plants in and around Los Angeles, Orange, San Bernadino, and Riverside counties that make up the Greater Los Angeles Area, boosting system resiliency and reliability. However, the main interest of this work is in examining the electric and gas

transmission systems in a zero emissions future.

The key findings from this work are:

1. Baseline Grid Resiliency:

- Simulations reveal that disabling critical electrical transmission zones can lead to severe overloads on transmission lines, with some exceeding 120% of operational limits for several hours. Potential events that could lead to disabled transmission zones are PSPS events, which could result in the preemptive de-energization of circuits during high wind/high fire danger events.
- Under baseline conditions, the Greater Los Angeles Area electrical grid struggles to maintain stability when major electric transmission corridors are disrupted, highlighting the need for enhanced resiliency measures. In particular, electric transmission line outages can be overcome by routing electricity through other electric transmission routes. However, this leads to transmission line overloads, increased electric transmission losses, and larger voltage drops across the electric transmission network.

2. Hydrogen as a Resiliency Measure:

- Hydrogen transported via existing gas pipelines demonstrates significant potential to alleviate electric grid overloads during transmission outages.
- When individual electrical transmission lines connecting the Greater Los Angeles Area to electrical generation in the Central Valley, Imperial Valley, Coachella Valley, and desert areas experience an outage, the current gas transmission system can transport sufficient hydrogen to power distributed generation (H₂ fuel cells), compensating for lost electrical transmission capacity, maintaining service to all demand nodes without exceeding pipeline capacity.
- For scenarios where multiple electrical transmission lines are offline, current gas pipelines cannot transmit the necessary hydrogen to keep the Greater Los Angeles Area electrical grid operational. Regardless, transmitting hydrogen to distributed generation inside the Greater Los Angeles Area reduces electric transmission overloads and maintained system functionality in all other cases.

3. Critical Load Management:

- The report evaluates scenarios where only critical loads—representing essential residential and commercial energy demands—are serviced during outages. These scenarios demonstrate that hydrogen pipelines can effectively ensure energy delivery to critical services, further enhancing resiliency.
- Critical load scenarios significantly reduce the strain on the grid, enabling the infrastructure to meet demand with fewer overloads and interruptions.

4. Transition to Renewable Energy:

- The report explores a scenario where all natural gas generation is replaced with hydrogen fuel cells, leveraging the pipeline network to supply renewable hydrogen.
- This hydrogen-enabled system successfully managed the energy demands of the Greater Los Angeles Area, even under simulated disruptions where electric transmission lines are taken offline due to PSPS events and/or equipment failure, and fossil fuel powerplants along the Southern California coastline are mothballed.

5. Electrification Impacts:

- Complete electrification of natural gas end-uses increases electrical loads significantly, placing additional strain on the electrical grid in the form of current overloads and voltage anomalies. The overloads are so high in magnitude that the natural gas infrastructure running in parallel to these overloaded electrical transmission lines are at full hydrogen transmission capacity, and are therefore not able to alleviate the electrical overloads.
- While the hydrogen infrastructure can accommodate these increased loads in most single-zone outage scenarios, simultaneous outages of major corridors like Zones 1 and 2 require additional infrastructure to maintain performance.

The integration of hydrogen as a resiliency measure not only bolsters the grid's ability to withstand disruptions but also aligns with California's goals of achieving 100% renewable energy by 2045. This approach capitalizes on the existing natural gas pipeline network to deliver renewable hydrogen, reducing the need for large-scale upgrades to electrical infrastructure while enhancing overall system flexibility.

To further enhance system resiliency:

- Integrate fuel cell energy systems into existing electrical substations located near existing natural gas transmission pipes.
- Expand hydrogen pipeline capacity in critical regions to address simultaneous outage scenarios.
- Incorporate hydrogen-based systems into long-term infrastructure planning to balance increasing electrification demands.
- Focus on critical load prioritization during extreme events to ensure essential services are maintained.

This study underscores the value of hydrogen as a transformative solution for energy system resiliency and the broader transition to a sustainable and decarbonized energy future.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

Resilient, reliable, and renewable energy infrastructure will be needed for many different industrial and commercial applications - such as data centers, hospitals, military facilities, and other essential services – currently located in urban environments where space constraints and expensive real estate are hurdles. Most of these applications have extremely strict and high standards for energy service uptime, which is jeopardized by the call for conversion towards more renewable energy resources, which are intermittent and fluctuating (e.g., solar and wind). In this effort, we aim to demonstrate that renewable hydrogen – in concert with a cheap and renewable power supply on the electric grid – provide the best solution to meet 100% renewable energy conversion goals, maintain firm power to critical and essential services, and maintain stringent reliability and resiliency requirements. The goal of this work is to analyze the application of renewable H₂ as a method to increase energy system resiliency and reliability for the entire Greater Los Angeles Area. This is achieved by leveraging the existing gas transmission system to transmit 100% renewable hydrogen, providing a clean power source to run distributed generation (H₂ fuel cells) that can produce electricity at or near point of use when there are electrical transmission system outages.

This work considers two separate sets of loads. First, we consider energy demands at all utility customers across the Greater Los Angeles Area. This includes the typical full load at each customer site, and loads that each customer may deem as “critical”, i.e., for residential customers, loads associated with food storage and preparation, lighting for safety, and internet/communications. Second, we consider critical infrastructure and essential services that currently maintain backup generation to guard against utility outages, such as hospitals, police stations, communication networks, water pumping stations, and traffic control systems.

To demonstrate the advantage of 1) improved energy system reliability and resiliency, and 2) the use of hydrogen to support critical infrastructure and essential services, it is fundamental to analyze not just the final end-use generation system, but its interaction with the coupled infrastructure. Our simulations involve the analysis of electrochemical energy conversion and storage devices – such as fuel cells, electrolyzers, batteries – and their dynamic coupling with local distributed renewable energy sources (e.g., solar PV), remote renewable energy sources, the electric grid, and the gas grid. The core of this effort is a complete model of the Southern California electrical and gas networks. These tools can be coupled to consider how utility grid outages can be overcome by installing H₂ fuel cells across the electrical grid where the fuel cells are powered by renewable H₂ flowing through the gas networks.

Finally, the effects that the designed energy system will have on the local society in terms of job creation/transfer, as well aspects related to societal acceptance will be evaluated. In particular, the key elements of energy security and environmental justice associated to the development of a demonstration system in a low-income or disadvantaged neighborhood will be investigated.

1.2 Literature Review

Resiliency (or resilience) as a quantity does not have a generally accepted definition in the literature. Many sources in the literature attempt to arrive at metrics to evaluate resiliency based on a definition from a technical report discussed by the IEEE [1]. This report defines resiliency as “The ability to withstand and reduce the magnitude and/or duration of disruptive events, which includes the capability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and/or rapidly recover from such an event.” Numerous papers that attempt to expand upon this definition are compiled and evaluated in a literature survey conducted by Chi Y. et al. [2]

Before discussing a set of sources, Chi conducts a re-evaluation of the conception of resiliency, using a table to draw comparisons between itself and reliability. Table 1 indicates that that resiliency is concerned with the operation of a system subjected to unusual events, whereas reliability evaluates typical operation of a system. As such, the fragility/survivability and restoration/recovery of infrastructure are highly relevant. Additionally, when evaluating resiliency, it is important to distinguish between typical loads and critical loads.

Table 1: Reliability vs. Resiliency [2]

Features	Reliability	Resilience
description	frequency and time duration	fragility, survivability, restoration
focus	load and generation	withstand and recover
acceptance	wide-accepted	no wide-accepted or well-defined
situation	computation based on a specific period	dynamic computation or immediately after an event
load	all loads	critical loads oriented
incident types	ignore short time incidents	more extensive scenarios
criterion	universal	situation based
specification	high probability, low impact	high impact, low probability
improvement	capital investment	operation strategy and investment
data source	extensive historical data	lack of field data

Chi states that resiliency is “a potential capability assessment of a system according to its operational modes” [2]. Therefore, by developing a model of an electrical transmission system and subjecting it to different conditions, we can quantify its resiliency based on its performance.

According to a topical report conducted by the Gas Technology Institute (GTI) [3], the average energy distribution reliability of natural gas infrastructure is significantly higher than that of electrical infrastructure. Specifically, the graph shown in Figure 1, sourced from this report, shows that natural gas infrastructure approaches six-sigma reliability, meaning unplanned outages affect 1 in 800 customers per year. The electrical distribution system is below five-sigma reliability, where each customer experiences one outage per year. Furthermore, the report states that anecdotally, it appears that most electric outages occur due to unplanned impacts such as severe weather, while most natural gas outages occur due to planned maintenance.

Figure 1: Average reliability and outage rate metrics for the electrical and natural gas networks across the United States

Climate Change is an observable phenomenon. Average global temperatures have been rising yearly since the Industrial Revolution. The impact of this increase in temperature is a higher frequency of natural disasters. In California, wildfire frequency and severity has seen an exponential increase in response to the rising temperatures. Between 1975 and 2018, annual burned area increased by 405% [4].

Public Safety Power Shutoff (PSPS) events are scheduled electrical outages in certain areas to reduce the risk of fires caused by electrical infrastructure [5]. PSPS events are necessary when weather conditions could cause the ignition of wildfires. High winds coupled with arid conditions are the biggest concern, as they could cause the swinging of dry shrubbery into nearby power lines. As the impact and frequency of wildfires has demonstrably grown, electrical utilities will likely be more inclined to enact PSPS events as preventative measures. This means that electrical customers can expect to experience a higher frequency of electrical outages.

According to the Energy Sector Risk Profile, a document procured by the U.S. Department of Energy [6], out of 118 electric transmission outages experienced between 1992 and 2008, 10 were

caused by wildfires, 8 by high winds, and 8 by heat waves. However, the report cites data collected by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, that indicates that wildfires are by far the costliest in California, responsible for \$164.1 million in property loss per year. Wildfires are seconded only by winter storms and extreme cold at \$101.7 million, though such events are not applicable to Southern California.

1.3 Current Work and Contributions

This work focuses on the electrical and natural gas networks in Los Angeles, Orange County, and parts of Riverside and Orange County. Geographical demarcation is based on the location of fire risk zones surrounding the major population centers in Southern California. Given the facts summarized in the prior section, the topic of interest for this report is recruiting natural gas infrastructure to cooperate with electrical infrastructure to leverage its superior reliability. Specific to the issue of wildfires, it would be difficult to come up with a situation where natural gas pipeline infrastructure could be responsible for igniting a fire. Thus, gas infrastructure could be used as a backup distribution system when part of the electrical infrastructure either fails or needs to be disabled. To achieve this, we can consider powering fuel cells using H₂ that is transported from points of production across California to points of use inside the Greater Los Angeles Area using existing gas transmission lines.

In essence, the methodology of this study will be to analyze the behavior of the Southern California electrical grid under various operating conditions, and then evaluate the ability of the natural gas pipeline infrastructure to help in delivering adequate energy to all demand nodes using hydrogen.

A major contribution of this work is the development of an electric transmission model for Southern California. Publicly available data sources were used to develop a highly detailed alternating current power flow representation of this system, including the magnitude and location of residential, commercial, and industrial electrical loads throughout Southern California.

To perform this study, a model previously developed to simulate transmitting H₂ using natural gas pipelines running on hydrogen was used [7]. This reference fully details the physics and execution of this gas pipeline model.

The contents of this report focus on the different resiliency analyses performed during this work. A complete description of the data collection methods and model development is provided in the Appendix.

2 Key Assumptions

The key assumptions made in this work are:

- Existing natural gas transmission and distribution pipes have been repurposed to carry 100% H₂. This implicitly assumes that:
 - California regulations have been amended to allow the injection and transmission of H₂ into existing gas pipelines
 - Gas transmission pipeline components can safely transmit H₂
 - Gas transmission components that cannot safely or reliably transmit H₂ have been replaced
 - Utility customers can safely use H₂ at their facilities/residences
 - There is a consistent and steady supply of renewable H₂ that can be injected into pipelines that serve the Southern California Gas service territory
 - H₂ can be produced and delivered to pipelines at a relatively low cost that would enable consumer use
- Utility customers have the ability to shed load during a resiliency event. We do not resolve how load shedding occurs – if there is a technology (i.e., smart panel or smart appliance/load) that enables automatic load shedding, or if individual utility customers actuate their loads to reduce demand during a resiliency event (i.e., unplug appliances, turn off air conditioner, turn off lights).
- Fuel cells are used as the H₂ distributed generation installed across the Greater Los Angeles Area to improve system resiliency and reliability.
- Natural gas power plants inside the Greater Los Angeles Area have been shut down. Specific scenarios assume that these power plants have been retrofitted to use H₂ or have been replaced with H₂ fuel cells.
- Transportation electrification is not considered

3 Electric and Natural Gas Transmission Infrastructure

This study is focused on infrastructure in the Southern California area – both electrical and natural gas. Maps showing the infrastructure that is considered are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 for the electrical and natural gas transmission systems respectively. Figure 2 also indicates major substations captured in the electrical transmission systems. These substations are located at points where the high voltage electrical transmission system interfaces with lower voltage transmission and distribution circuits. Electrical loads across the Southern California Edison territory are aggregated around these major substations indicated in Figure 2. The substations in Figure 2 are split between substations that are also connected to utility scale natural gas electricity generation, and substations that are not.

Figure 2: Map of the Southern California electrical transmission grid with major substations. All substations serve electrical utility customers either directly or through other substations that are connected through lower voltage transmission and distribution circuits not captured in this map. Substations are differentiated between substations that are connected to utility scale natural gas electricity generation, and substations that are not.

Figure 3: Southern California gas transmission network

4 Resiliency Analysis

To evaluate the resiliency of the electrical grid as it stands, we refer to Table 1, which states that resiliency can be partially quantified by a metric to describe the fragility/survivability of the electrical grid, specifically in unusual conditions. It has been demonstrated in practice that the grid is capable of operating when all lines are active, and the model reflects this. However, when subjected to a ‘disruptive event’ as referred to by IEEE in [1] in which normal operation of the grid is affected in ways that can lead to power outages, voltage instabilities, or system failures, the grid may be unable to respond depending on the magnitude of the event. Common types of disruptive events include natural disasters and extreme weather, cybersecurity and physical attacks, equipment failures, unexpected or excessive electric demand, and operational/human errors.

The key result presented in this section is that the loss of major electric transmission lines has the potential to reduce the reliability of the Southern California electric grid, potentially leading to a resiliency event. Under current load conditions, additional demand response is absolutely necessary if other measures are not taken to ensure grid resiliency and reliability against wildfires and other PSPS causing events.

4.1 Wildfire/PSPS Event Zones

In 2023, there were a total of 13 Public Safety Power Shutoff (PSPS) events. At least one PSPS event occurred in August of 2023. In Los Angeles, August saw the highest average temperature of all months in 2023 ([8]), meaning the cooling loads were likely higher than normal. Therefore, analysis of PSPS events coupled with the elevated August load profiles is most pertinent to the evaluation of the grid’s resiliency, as it provides results for a ‘worst-case’ scenario.

Figure 4: PSPS Events in 2023

The DERiM resource as discussed in Appendix B provides a map of areas that have high fire risk. Transmission lines running through these areas are therefore candidates for shutoffs. Figure 5 shows a map of the fire hazard areas surrounding the LA basin, as well as the electrical infrastructure running through these areas. The fire areas were partitioned into 5 zones. Figure 6 shows these partitioned fire risk areas. All transmission lines in the model that run through these areas were grouped together based on zone. To simulate PSPS events, the lines running through each zone could be disabled depending on which zone was flagged to be a wildfire threat. While PSPS events are outages scheduled to prevent the ignition of a wildfire by transmission infrastructure, this zone analysis doubles as a potential scenario where a wildfire does occur in these zones, leading to the destruction of the corresponding transmission infrastructure. In analyzing the resiliency of the system to PSPS events, the model will be run with both individually disabled as well as combinations of disabled zones.

Figure 5: Southern California Fire Hazard Areas

Figure 6: Partitioned Fire Zones

A variety of outage scenarios are considered in this work. These scenarios also consider different generation scenarios where the natural gas electrical generators located inside Los Angeles, Orange, Riverside, and San Bernadino county are kept operational using natural gas or converted to hydrogen. These different scenarios are listed in Table 2. This table also provides a high level summary on simulation results, indicating if electric transmission overloads occur in the simulation

and if existing gas pipelines could carry the necessary quantity of hydrogen. Additional information in this table include:

- **Electric Load Definition:** This describes the electric load scenario across Southern California. “Base” indicates electric loads based on current electricity use in Southern California. “Critical” indicates that a resiliency event is occurring and electric loads have been curtailed to “critical loads only”. “100% Electrified” indicates that most residential, commercial, and industrial natural gas loads have been electrified and have been added to the normal electric load defined in the “Base” scenario.
- **Generation Fuel:** This indicates the type of fuel used to power the current natural gas generation located at substations as indicated with red dots in Figure 2. In the “H2” scenario, we assume that these generators can be repowered with hydrogen.
- **Disabled Zones:** Zones refer to fire zones shown in Figure 6. If a zone is disabled, we assume that all major transmission lines running through this fire zone are deenergized.
- **Overloads:** This indicates results from our simulations for the electric transmission system. A “Yes” indicates that the electrical transmission system experiences an overload somewhere in the system within this scenario.
- **Pipeline Success:** This indicates if the existing natural gas infrastructure can safely handle the gas that is required to meet customer and power plant fuel demand. A “N/A” indicates that the scenario assumes natural gas is flowing through the pipelines. Since the current natural gas system can handle customer and power plant demand, these scenarios are assumed to be viable and are not simulated. A “Yes” indicates that natural gas in all pipelines has been replaced with hydrogen, and the pipelines can handle the hydrogen demand. A “No” indicates that natural gas in all pipelines has been replaced with hydrogen, and the current system does not have sufficient gas carrying capacity to supply the desired fuel energy flow rate. A “Partially” indicates that natural gas in all pipelines has been replaced with hydrogen, and that the gas pipeline system can handle the fuel transition through most hours of the day, but must be augmented with fuel storage near or at the customer to successfully meet demand. In other words, the gas pipeline system in the “Partially” case can handle the average gas demand, but cannot handle peak gas demand.

Table 2: Definition of different generation and outage scenarios. The table also indicates if electric transmission system overloads occur, if the pipeline is capable of carrying the desired hydrogen, and the section that describes the scenario

Scenario Index	Electric Load Definition	Generation Fuel	Disabled Zones	Overloads	Pipeline Success	Report Section
1	Base	Base	None	No	N/A	N/A
2	Base	Base	1	No	N/A	4.2.1
3	Base	Base	2	No	N/A	4.2.2
4	Base	Base	3	Yes	N/A	4.2.3
5	Base	Base	4	Yes	N/A	4.2.4
6	Base	Base	3,4	Yes	N/A	4.2.5
7	Base	Base	5	Yes	N/A	4.2.6
8	Critical	Base	3	Yes	N/A	4.3.4
9	Critical	Base	4	Yes	N/A	4.3.5
10	Critical	Base	5	No	N/A	4.3.6
11	Base	H ₂	None	Yes	N/A	5.2
12	Base	H ₂	1	Yes	Yes	5.7.1
13	Base	H ₂	2	Yes	Yes	5.7.2
14	Base	H ₂	1,2	Yes	No	5.7.3
15	Base	H ₂	3	Yes	Yes	5.7.4
16	Base	H ₂	4	Yes	Partially	5.7.5
17	Base	H ₂	5	Yes	Partially	5.7.6
18	100% Electrified	H ₂	1,2	Yes	No	6.1

4.2 Resiliency of the Existing Electrical Grid/Model Verification

The base system, which includes August load and generation profiles, must first be assessed for resiliency to these PSPS events. First, each of the five previously specified zones will be disabled, leading to five simulations where a major transmission pathway is offline. After this, combinations of two disabled zones will be simulated. OpenDSS requires the specification of a “source bus”, which compensates for any net load in the system by providing importation or exportation as if the system is a microgrid connected to a larger grid. In all simulations, this source bus has been selected to be the easternmost bus in Palm Springs. This bus was chosen because of the implications of potentially placing renewable generation in the adjacent desert and evaluating the ability of the transmission corridors there to transport this generation to the basin. Each of the five established fire risk zones will be disabled individually and the resulting circuit will be evaluated based on performance.

4.2.1 Zone 1 - Lower Palm Springs Corridor

Zone 1 is the lower Palm Springs corridor. Figure 7 shows that disabling it has no significant impact on the Greater Los Angeles area circuits, as there are no reported current overloads, nor voltage anomalies. This is a reasonable result, as the transmission lines in the Palm Springs corridor are robust, but not responsible for much power transmission within this configuration, as there is less than 2GW of generation in the area. The key driver of this result is that other electric transmission lines have sufficient current-carrying capacities to supply the electricity that would have otherwise been supplied through the lower Palm Springs corridor without inducing a line overload or experiencing unacceptable voltage drop throughout the electric transmission system.

Figure 7: Base Loads & Generation Overload Plot (Zone 1 Disabled)

4.2.2 Zone 2 - Upper Palm Springs Corridor

Figure 8 shows that disabling Zone 2, the upper transmission corridor in Palm Springs, leads to no overload or voltage anomaly reports.

Figure 8: Base Loads & Generation Overload Plot (Zone 2 Disabled)

4.2.3 Zone 3 – Victorville Corridor

A significant importation corridor runs through Zone 3. Specifically, Path 27, which has a transmission capacity of 2.4MW, is set to supply 1.2GW of power to the circuit in the current setup of the generation profiles. When Zone 3 is disabled, Path 27 is cut off, and the source bus must provide both active and reactive power to compensate. As can be seen from Figure 9 and Table 3, various sections of the network experience electrical overloads. These overloads are the result of the loss of 1.2GW of imported power through Path 27, which is compensated for by the source bus in Palm Springs.

Figure 9: Base Loads & Generation Overload Plot (Zone 3 Disabled)

Table 3: Base Loads & Generation Voltage Report (Zone 3 Disabled)

Maximum Over-voltage	Maximum Hour	Number of Over-voltages at Max Hour	Minimum Under-voltage	Minimum Hour	Number of Under-voltages at Min Hour
1.048181	18	0	0.992877	5	0

Table 4: Base Loads & Generation Overload Report (Zone 3 Disabled)

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
5743	500	0	TRUE	3223	118	6	483
5741	500	0	FALSE	3223	118	6	483
5742	500	0	FALSE	3223	118	6	483
3622	220	8	FALSE	4054	116	3	574
5744	220	10	TRUE	2599	112	3	279
3654	500	7	TRUE	3216	117	3	476

4.2.4 Zone 4 – Santa Clarita Corridor

The lines running through Zone 4 include Path 65, the other major source of imported power. In the model, it supplies a constant 1.55GW to the grid. With Zone 4 disabled, the circuit experiences overloads specifically in the Victorville corridor. This is because a significant amount of generation originates North that no longer has a direct path to substations in the city, and instead must take a detour through the Victorville corridor. The overloads are relatively small, not exceeding 120% of operating capacity but lasting between 4 and 6 hours.

Figure 10: Base Loads & Generation Overload Plot (Zone 4 Disabled)

Table 5: Base Loads & Generation Overload Report (Zone 4 Disabled)

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3597	500	76	FALSE	3198	117	6	458
3598	500	76	FALSE	3196	117	6	456
3892	500	20	TRUE	4802	117	6	692
3893	500	2	TRUE	3217	117	6	477
3894	500	1	FALSE	6437	117	6	957
3889	500	26	FALSE	3190	116	6	450
3891	500	26	FALSE	3205	117	6	465
3890	500	31	FALSE	3145	115	4	405

Table 6: Base Loads & Generation Voltage Report (Zone 4 Disabled)

Maximum Over-voltage	Maximum Hour	Number of Over-voltages at Max Hour	Minimum Under-voltage	Minimum Hour	Number of Under-voltages at Min Hour
1.052954	16	7	0.988695	10	0

To simulate a situation where the utility disables the overloaded lines, we can disable both Zones 3 and 4 at the same time. This includes the loss of both sources of imported power, as well as a significant amount of current carrying capacity. As can be seen in Figure 11, the Palm Springs corridors are still capable of transmitting the 3.75GW of power lost when the import routes are cut off. However, downstream in the city, the transmission infrastructure cannot handle these conditions.

Figure 11: Base Loads & Generation Overload Plot (Zones 3 and 4 Disabled)

4.2.5 Zone 5 – Central Corridor

The final fire risk zone is in the center of the map. The results show only two overloads, both under 120% of operating capacity, yet lasting 4 and 5 hours. More significantly, there is a large amount of over-voltages occurring at hour 17. While the transmission lines, spare the overloaded lines, can handle these conditions, other transmission infrastructure may be damaged by these voltage anomalies.

Figure 12: Base Loads & Generation Overload Plot (Zone 5 Disabled)

Table 7: Base Loads & Generation Overload Report (Zone 5 Disabled)

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3876	220	7	FALSE	2744	118	5	424
3896	220	8	TRUE	2583	111	4	263

Table 8: Base Loads & Generation Voltage Report (Zone 5 Disabled)

Maximum Over-voltage	Maximum Hour	Number of Over-voltages at Max Hour	Minimum Under-voltage	Minimum Hour	Number of Under-voltages at Min Hour
1.076172	17	177	0.989671	17	0

4.2.6 Conclusions on Existing Grid Resiliency Under Full Loads

The analysis conducted in this section has provided insight into the grid's ability to service typical full electrical loads in cases where significant transmission corridors are disabled. Overall, disabling these corridors individually did have a negative impact on overall grid stability. Transmission line outages can be survived by overloading other transmission lines serving the Southern California region. In most cases, overloads exceed rated equipment capacity by 20%, which may be survivable as long as extreme heat events do not coincide with the outage.

4.3 Residential & Commercial Building Stock Critical Loads

We consider two types of critical loads in this work. First, there is the general set of critical and essential services necessary for the functioning of society during extreme events, including emergency response, healthcare facilities, water and wastewater treatment, telecommunications, and transportation infrastructure. Second, we consider loads that individual utility customers would consider as "essential". At the residential and commercial level, loads associated with medical equipment are also considered critical and are typically met with the help of onsite backup generation. However, outages lasting longer than half a day can have direct financial, quality of life, and health/safety impacts on populations outside of those directly affected by electrical and other energy infrastructure outages. In this sense, we extend "critical" loads to also include critical residential and commercial loads beyond immediate life saving medical loads.

The system has performed decently under the duress of the removal of significant transmission corridors. Referring to Table 1, resiliency is a measurement more concerned with the serviceability of critical loads rather than whole loads. A scenario therefore worth exploring is one where only end-uses that are considered critical are included in the load profiles, thereby reducing the overall loads and decreasing the stress on the electrical grid. If the system can perform well in such a situation, it is considered resilient. To construct such load profiles, we leverage the ResStock & ComStock load profile breakdowns discussed in 0.

4.3.1 Residential Load Profile

The ResStock residential load profile can be broken down into a set of end-uses, of which several could be considered critical. Below is a table of each end use, whether it is or is not considered critical in the analysis, and a rationale.

Table 9: Residential End Uses

END USE	CRITICAL?	REASONING
CEILING FAN	Y	Some buildings may not be equipped with A/C, fan is last resort for cooling
CLOTHES DRYER	N	Clothes can be hang-dried
CLOTHES WASHER	N	Clothes can be washed in bathtub
COOLING	Y	Livable indoor temperature is critical
DISHWASHER	N	Dishes can be washed in sink
FREEZER	Y	Storage of food is essential
HEATING	Y	Temperature control is essential
HOT TUB	N	Recreational item
HOT WATER	Y	Necessary for washing
EXTERIOR LIGHTING	Y	Exterior visibility at night promotes safety
INTERIOR LIGHTING	Y	Visibility in home promotes safety
GARAGE LIGHTING	Y	Same as interior lighting
MECHANICAL VENTS	Y	May be important to be able to close vents in the case of wildfires affecting air quality
PLUG LOADS	50%	Internet connection, as well as some critical end uses, may be tied to this
POOL HEATING	N	Recreational item
RANGE OVEN	Y	Ability to cook food is essential
REFRIGERATOR	Y	Storage of food is essential
WELL PUMP	Y	Ability to pump water is essential

4.3.2 Commercial Load Profile

As with ResStock's breakdown, ComStock can be broken down into end uses. All end uses are assumed to be critical because their naming indicates they are all tied to either lighting, heating, cooling, or some other system whose importance of operability is ambiguous.

4.3.3 Adjusting Load Profiles

To generate a critical load profile for each substation, the existing base load profile for that substation is multiplied by a factor at each hour. For each hour, the percentage of the total load deemed critical, based on the assertions made in sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.2, is close to 80%. This

20% reduction may be enough to alleviate some of the overloads experienced when disabling the zones. Figure 13 shows the resulting critical load profile for one of the substations. There is a consistent decrease in the load for each hour. Zones 3, 4 and 5 showed to cause problems when disabled in the full load case examined. They will again be tested under the reduced critical load.

Figure 13: Base & Critical Load Profile Comparison

4.3.4 Zone 3

Figure 14: Zone 3 Performance Under Critical Loads, Overload Plot

Table 10: Zone 3 Performance Under Critical Loads, Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
5743	500	0	TRUE	3125	114	4	385
5741	500	0	FALSE	3125	114	4	385
5742	500	0	FALSE	3125	114	4	385
3622	220	8	FALSE	3894	112	3	414
3654	500	7	TRUE	3108	113	3	368
5744	220	10	TRUE	2497	108	2	177

Despite the reduction in load, the same lines are overloaded, although in comparison with the results for Zone 3 in 4.2.3, the overloads are reduced slightly in percentage and significantly in duration.

4.3.5 Zone 4

Figure 15: Zone 4 Performance Under Critical Loads, Overload Plot

Table 11: Zone 4 Performance Under Critical Loads, Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3597	500	76	FALSE	3112	114	6	372

3598	500	76	FALSE	3110	114	6	370
3892	500	20	TRUE	4678	114	4	568
3893	500	2	TRUE	3134	114	4	394
3894	500	1	FALSE	6270	114	4	790
3889	500	26	FALSE	3106	113	4	366
3890	500	31	FALSE	3062	112	4	322
3891	500	26	FALSE	3120	114	4	380

As with the performance of Zone 3, there is a marginal reduction in the overload percentage and a significant decrease in the overload duration.

4.3.6 Zone 5

Figure 16: Zone 5 Performance Under Critical Loads, Overload Report

Under critical loads, disabling Zone 5 no longer leads to overloads.

4.3.7 Conclusions on Critical Load Resiliency

Despite the 20% reduction in loads, there are still significant overloads that occur when Zones 3 and 4 are disabled. To fully avoid overloads in such a scenario, the reduced electrical load would have to be decreased further beyond the critical residential and commercial loads outlined in Section 4.3.1, which could be a realistic strategy as 80% is a generous estimate of what portion of loads should be considered critical.

5 Pipeline Hydrogen as a Resiliency Augmentation

California aims to transition to 100% renewable energy by 2045. A scenario of interest is therefore one where the non-renewable generation in the model is disabled entirely. In the model, this implies the removal of all natural gas generation. Can this lost generation be replaced by renewable generation sited in locations outside of the Greater Los Angeles Area? More specifically, will the electrical transmission infrastructure be able to support the added strain resulting from the removal of in-basin generation? If not, how can the natural gas infrastructure be leveraged to accomplish this?

The analysis in this section differs from the prior because the prior section only considered if the current electrical transmission system can successfully handle transmission line outages. In many instances, the electric transmission system experiences overloads and voltage issues. This section introduces a remedy to transmission issues during a resiliency event where the gas transmission system is used to deliver hydrogen to fuel cells and zero emission generators located across the Greater Los Angeles Area.

5.1 Combining Models

To introduce hydrogen as a renewable energy transmission medium, the existing natural gas infrastructure could be leveraged to deliver hydrogen to key points in the electrical transmission grid. Since the state of California is pushing its constituents to transition from non-renewable to renewable energy, a most logical step is to replace all natural gas generation with hydrogen fuel cells, supplied with hydrogen through the pipeline network. The California State Geoportal, mentioned in 4, provides a geospatial dataset for the natural gas pipeline infrastructure in Southern California.

Figure 17 shows the natural gas pipeline network overlaid on the electrical transmission network of the model. The yellow substations host all natural gas generation in the model. As can be seen, the natural gas pipelines run close to many of these substations. Therefore, to conduct an analysis on the resiliency of the system when hydrogen transmission is included, all natural gas plants will be removed from the model, and a subset of the yellow substations that run closest to natural gas pipelines will be equipped with fuel cells to meet the duty cycle of the now inactive natural gas plants. The pipeline model will be used to evaluate whether the pipelines can transmit the necessary volume of hydrogen to power these fuel cells. Only pipes 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 in will be simulated as they cover the path from Palm Springs to a set of junctions in the basin that branch off into many other pipelines. Once the hydrogen is transported to these junctions, it is assumed that the pipeline infrastructure within the basin can distribute it.

Figure 17: Southern California Gas Pipeline & Electrical Infrastructure

5.2 System Response to Removal of Non-Renewables

To evaluate the ability to phase out non-renewable generation and replace it with hydrogen, it is important to determine the system response to the removal of natural gas generation. Natural gas is responsible for a significant portion of generation, thus its removal will have a major impact on the delicately balanced system.

Figure 18: Removal of Natural Gas Generation Overload Plot (Base Loads)

Table 12: Removal of Natural Gas Generation Overload Report (Base Loads)

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3568	500	67	FALSE	4235	155	7	1495
5698	500	66	FALSE	4288	156	7	1548
3653	500	65	FALSE	6011	146	6	1901
3569	220	69	FALSE	2464	106	2	144
3553	220	68	TRUE	2515	108	2	195

With the duress of the full loads as derived from CAISO historical data, removing in-basin natural gas plants puts significant stress on the Palm Springs transmission corridors when this missing generation is supplied by the source bus. Before running a more complicated approach, we can determine simply whether the pipelines that run parallel to these transmission lines are able to alleviate these overloads.

5.3 Leveraging Pipeline Hydrogen

The overloaded lines are not constantly overloaded. Below is an example of the ampacity profile on one of the overloaded lines. Figure 19 shows that line 3568 is overloaded from hour 13.5 onwards, peaking at hour 20.

Figure 19: Line 3568 Ampacity Plot

To alleviate this overload from the line, we convert this amperage first to power, then to hydrogen.

$$P = I_L \cdot V_{L-L} \cdot \sqrt{3} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = \frac{P \cdot SF}{LHV_{H_2} \cdot \eta_{GTP}} \quad (2)$$

Equation (1) converts single-phase current to three-phase power using the line-line (base) voltage. To obtain hydrogen mass flow rate, Equation (2) then takes this three-phase power and divides it by the lower heating value of hydrogen gas, as well as a conversion efficiency constant. It is then multiplied by a safety factor, to ensure that the line is not operating exactly at its operating capacity for those hours. These equations are applied to the profiles for each of the overloaded lines that run in parallel. For example, the lines from 339 to 347 in Figure 18 (3568, 5698, 3569, 3553 and 3554 in Figure 20) are included in this calculation, but the line from 347 to 367 is not, because this would be double counting the overload running through that branch. The lower heating value used is 120MJ/kg. A safety factor of 1.1 is assigned. A gas-to-power efficiency of 50% is assumed, based on known electrical efficiency data on PEMFCs ([9]). Therefore, the necessary power is converted to a theoretical hydrogen mass flow rate that would produce an equal power output when sent through a fuel cell.

Figure 20: Overloaded Line Ampacities

Figure 21 shows the resulting necessary hydrogen profile to alleviate the overloaded lines. This profile serves as a direct input into the pipeline model. Based on Figure 17, a simple network of a handful of pipes will be able to describe the pipeline system running in parallel with the overloaded lines. suggests the presence of pipes 1, 2, and 3 that meet at a compressor station, from where pipes 4 and 5 continue into the basin. It can be assumed that once the hydrogen has successfully passed through this set of pipes, the pipeline infrastructure in the basin, which hosts significantly more pipes as seen in Figure 17, can transmit the hydrogen to the different substations equipped with fuel cells. Assuming the ability to inject hydrogen into pipes 1, 2, and 3 in Palm Springs, we can use the MATLAB model discussed in section 1.3 coupled with corresponding pipeline parameters taken from to determine whether the pipeline network can transmit the hydrogen mass flow rate profile.

Figure 21: Hydrogen Mass Flow Rate

5.3.1 Segment 1 – Palm Springs to Compressor Station

The length of the pipeline segment between the Palm Springs injection point and the compressor station was assumed to be 100km, around 40% of the total length of the three pipelines according to . This assumption was made conservatively based on an observation of the distance between Palm Springs and the compressor station. Each of the three pipes can individually transmit the entire hydrogen mass flow rate, although the peak does approach the operational pipe pressure limit in pipes 1 and 3. These figures indicate the maximum pressure allowable in the pipe, the outlet pressure required at point of delivery, and the inlet pressure, or the pressure at which the gas is injected into the pipe.

Figure 22: Pipeline Segment 1 Performance, Full Mass Flow Rate

Dividing the mass flow rate among each pipeline based on diameter, which would be a physical approach to transmitting the hydrogen, naturally leads to better performance.

Figure 23: Pipeline Segment 1 Performance, Divided Mass Flow Rate

Evidently, if the mass flow rate is divided amongst the three pipelines in segment 1, the system can easily transmit the necessary hydrogen.

5.3.2 Segment 2 – Compressor Station to Basin

Figure 24 shows that the two pipelines connecting the compressor station to a station in the basin can easily support the hydrogen mass flow rate when it is divided among them equally. Despite the indicated lengths of pipes 4 and 5 being 60 and 68 miles respectively, the pipes are both assumed to be 100km for simplicity. Each pipe would also be able to support the full hydrogen mass flow rate individually, as seen from the performance of pipes 1 and 3 in Figure 22, which have the same diameters, lengths and pressure limits as pipes 4 and 5.

Figure 24: Pipeline Segment 2 Performance, Divided Mass Flow Rate

5.4 Simulating the Inclusion of Hydrogen Within OpenDSS

While the results so far suggest that pipeline hydrogen is an adequate resiliency booster in alleviating excess amperage loads across the transmission corridors originating from Palm Springs, the electrical grid is a dynamic system that may not respond ideally to the strategy. The outlet hydrogen mass flow rate profile can be reconverted back to an electrical load profile using the previously discussed equations, and this profile can be serviced by the introduction of fuel cells in the Greater Los Angeles Area.

In Figure 25, the yellow substations indicate substations initially equipped with natural gas plants. To simulate the inclusion of the pipeline hydrogen transmission, these substations will be equipped with fuel cells. For these substations, natural gas generation capacity values are summed, after which each substation is assigned a fractional value equal to their generation capacity divided by this summed total, to distribute the complete hydrogen generation profile among them. Finally, they are equipped with theoretical fuel cells with an electrical efficiency of 50% that produce a generation profile matching the total hydrogen generation profile. For substations that are not physically close to the shown transmission pipelines, it is assumed they receive their hydrogen via smaller distribution pipelines.

Figure 25: Electrical Grid, Natural Gas Pipelines, Natural Gas Plants

The electrical transmission model built using OpenDSS does not respond ideally to the inclusion of the hydrogen powered generation profile. While most overloads are alleviated, some electric transmission lines carry a higher than normal ampacity in order to deliver power to areas that would otherwise be powered through the Palm Springs electrical transmission lines. This higher ampacity leads to increased losses that are compensated for by increasing hydrogen supply, resulting in higher fuel cell power.

Figure 26: Remaining Overloads

To address this problem, we can simply add more hydrogen.

Figure 27: Additional Hydrogen to Address Overloads

By adding this hydrogen, the circuit should become overload free. Figure 28 shows the previously overloaded lines after the final hydrogen mass flow rate profile was implemented.

Figure 28: Previously Overloaded Lines After Hydrogen Implementation

The circuit is free of overloads, and we can now test whether the pipeline system can transmit this final mass flow rate. Figure 29 demonstrates the system performance with this new mass flow rate profile.

Figure 29: Pipeline System Performance With Final Hydrogen Mass Flow Rate, Divided

The pipeline system is fully capable of transmitting the necessary hydrogen to alleviate overloads on the electrical grid when non-renewable generation in the basin is replaced with fuel cells. However, this conclusion has not accounted for commercial and residential demand for energy that has been historically supplied using natural gas. We have assumed that all gas loads have transitioned from natural gas to hydrogen, and that in some instances, these gas loads will continue to be met using gas. However, all systems, including residential and commercial gas end uses, are repowered using hydrogen. This will be discussed in the next section.

5.5 Including Natural Gas Demand

It cannot be assumed that the pipelines are completely empty and only need to transmit the hydrogen profile obtained in 5.4. While the need for natural gas in utility generation has been eliminated with the removal of natural gas plants in the basin, residential and commercial demand for natural gas still exists. ResStock & ComStock, as discussed in 4, have simulated natural gas demand profiles for both sectors on an average August day. These profiles are provided in equivalent kWh of energy, making their conversion to hydrogen straightforward. Since this data represents the entire state of California, it is divided by three to represent an estimate of the demand of the area of the study. These residential and commercial natural gas kWh profiles are summed up and converted to hydrogen, assuming a gas-to-power efficiency of 30%. This low efficiency is a conservative estimate of how the end uses normally serviced by natural gas would perform on a 100% hydrogen input. The resulting hydrogen profile is added on top of the previous profile, and the system is reassessed. Figure 30 shows that the residential and commercial natural gas equivalent hydrogen demand are relatively small compared to the required hydrogen output for the overloaded lines.

Figure 30: Hydrogen Profiles

After combining these profiles, they are fed through the pipeline system.

Figure 31: System Performance Under Full Hydrogen Load

The system can easily support the complete hydrogen mass flow rate profile that includes residential and commercial natural gas demand. In conclusion, the natural gas pipeline infrastructure would be able to support the necessary hydrogen transmission to power fuel cells to fully replace the natural gas generation in the Greater Los Angeles Area. If Segment 2 can successfully transmit the hydrogen, this means that Segment 1 automatically can as well. Since Pipes 4 and 5 are assumed to have identical physical properties, we can assess the entire system performance from just one of these pipes alone. Thus, from here onwards, only Pipe 4 will be plotted for analysis purposes.

5.6 Fuel Cell Sizing Problem

We have established that the pipeline infrastructure can carry the necessary hydrogen to the substations. However, to convert this hydrogen back into electricity to be injected into the grid, adequate fuel cell capacity is necessary. Based on the simulated hydrogen generation profile established for the base system in section 5.5, each of the substations requires 10s t0 1000s of MW fuel cell capacity. According to the Fuel Cell & Hydrogen Energy Association (FCHE, [10]), stationary fuel cell technology can produce around 10MW per acre of land. Assuming a linear relationship between power output and the area required, the substations would each require tens to hundreds of acres of space, land which is not readily available in the city. Furthermore, this is only considering the base circuit, not the added strain of disabling Zones, which would increase the required fuel cell power output even more.

Instead of assuming the use of fuel cells, a near term solution would be to switch to H₂ powered combined cycles using conventional gas turbine and steam turbine systems. Conventional combined cycles can operate at peak fuel to electricity conversion efficiencies exceeding 60%. Long term solutions could include higher efficiency fuel cell – gas turbine cycles where a high temperature fuel cell is thermally integrated with a gas turbine, using heat from the fuel cell process to replace combustion in a gas turbine. Theoretical analysis of this next generation power plant predict fuel to electricity conversion efficiencies in excess of 70% on a lower heating value basis ([11]). Several experimental fuel cell-gas turbine hybrids have successfully demonstrated efficiencies approaching and exceeding these theoretical values ([12]). For this work, we assume that power plants with a fuel to electricity conversion efficiency of 55% are used. This lower value is selected based on a) existing generators in the Greater Los Angeles Area that could be repowered using hydrogen, and b) to reflect that power plants operating on a electric grid with high penetration of intermittent renewable resources are regularly operated at part load where actual efficiency drops below rated efficiency.

Based on this new efficiency assumption, the final hydrogen profile needed to supply the system after natural gas is completely removed is plotted below.

Figure 32: Base System Hydrogen Profile

As Pipe 4 can transmit its share of the hydrogen mass flow profile, we can conclude that the entire pipeline system does as well.

5.7 Resiliency of Resulting System

Now that the pipeline has an active role in the energy transmission system, we can conduct the same analysis done in Section 4. Each of the five fire risk zones is disabled, the resulting overloads are plotted, and the question of whether the pipeline can support enough hydrogen to alleviate these overloads by supplying combined cycle hydrogen plants is answered, for both the full electrical loads as well as the critical loads established in 4.3. The results in this section consider the addition of H₂ in the gas transmission system as a fuel that can be used in backup generation and other systems that can be used to send electricity back to the grid during an adverse electric transmission event.

5.7.1 Zone 1 - Pipeline Included

Figure 33 shows overloads are experienced in the upper Palm Springs corridor under full electrical loads when zone 1 is disabled. In this situation, the pipelines running in parallel to the transmission lines are ideal for addressing the overloads. Taking the same approach as before, the amperage overloads on the transmission lines tabulated in

Table 12 are converted to an equivalent hydrogen mass flow rate and then sent through the pipelines, on top of the mass flow rate established in section 5.5. By doing this, ideally the electrical overloads are addressed by the additional hydrogen mass flow into the basin. Figure 33 shows the circuit response to the removal of the lower transmission corridor, when there is no natural gas generation in the basin. Naturally, since that natural gas generation is replaced by renewable generation originating from bus 339, an electrical overload occurs in the other transmission corridor. Sections 5.7.1.1 and 5.7.1.2 show the ability of the pipeline to address this issue for full electrical loads and critical loads respectively.

Figure 33: Zone 1 Disabled – System Overload Plot

Table 13: Zone 1 Disabled – Pipeline-Included Electrical Performance Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3896	220	8	TRUE	2546	110	1	226
3876	220	7	FALSE	2705	117	1	385
3555	220	25	TRUE	2949	127	2	629
3556	220	25	TRUE	2913	126	2	593
3873	220	24	FALSE	3010	130	2	690
3569	220	69	FALSE	3494	151	2	1174
3553	220	68	TRUE	3565	154	2	1245
3554	220	72	TRUE	3353	145	2	1033

5.7.1.1 Disabling Zone 1 Under Full Electrical Loads

First, the system is evaluated based on its ability to transmit adequate hydrogen to meet full electrical loads. Figure 34 shows the resulting necessary hydrogen mass flow rate that eliminates the overloads in the circuit that arise when Zone 1 is disabled, under full electrical loads. Logically, the removal of transmission infrastructure running parallel to the pipelines has increased the involvement of the pipelines in energy transmission. This total profile will be sent through the pipeline system.

Figure 34: Hydrogen Mass Flow Rate for Full Load Zone 1

Figure 35 shows the performance of the pipeline system on the necessary hydrogen mass flow rate under full electrical loads. Since Pipe 4 can transmit its portion of the hydrogen mass flow, Pipe 5 is also capable, and therefore Pipes 1, 2 and 3 are as well.

Figure 35: Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zone 1

5.7.1.2 Disabling Zone 1 Under Critical Loads

Since the pipelines can support hydrogen under full electrical loads, the ability to service critical loads is implied. As Figure 36 shows, under critical loads the pipeline is even more capable of transmitting the necessary hydrogen to the basin.

Figure 36: Pipeline Performance Report, Critical Loads, Zone 1

5.7.2 Zone 2 – Pipeline Included

Figure 37: Zone 2 Disabled – System Overload Plot

Table 14: Zone 2 Disabled – Pipeline-Included Electrical Performance Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3568	500	67	FALSE	4004	146	3	1264
5698	500	66	FALSE	4055	148	3	1315
3653	500	65	FALSE	5860	143	1	1750

Figure 38: Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zone 2

When Zone 2 is disabled, the pipeline is again fully capable of transmitting the necessary hydrogen to alleviate circuit overloads. Its involvement is less than when Zone 1 was disabled, because the transmission capacity in Zone 1 is higher than in Zone 2. Based on this performance report and the conclusions made from 5.7.1.2, we know the system will be able to service critical loads easily and do not need to run a simulation.

5.7.3 Zones 1 AND 2 – Pipeline Included

With the inclusion of the pipeline system, we can now look at a case that we could not simulate before, where both Zones 1 and 2 are disabled at the same time, meaning there is no electrical transmission infrastructure connecting the renewable generation in Palm Springs to the main electrical grid. The pipeline would be required to meet the full lost transmission capacity of both Zones, which may lead to it exceeding its operational limits. Figure 39 confirms the suspected outcome of removing both Zones 1 and 2. Without any electrical transmission capacity running between the generation site in the desert and the LA basin, the pipeline system on its own exceeds its operational limit between hours 12 and 24.

Figure 39: Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zones 1 and 2

Even if storage were considered, peak-shaving and valley-filling as a strategy would not work because the total mass of hydrogen transmitted during the overloaded period exceeds the transmission capacity when the pipe is not overloaded.

Instead, we can consider the possibility of building additional pipeline infrastructure. To determine whether multiple pipeline additions will be necessary, we must evaluate the entire system rather than just Pipe 4.

Figure 40: Complete Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zones 1 and 2

In Segment 1, Pipes 1 and 3 hit their operational limit. However, since Pipe 2, with a larger diameter and higher pressure limit, is not close to its limit, we could reduce the transmission through Pipes 1 and 3 and redirect it through Pipe 2 such that none of them reach their limit. Thus, Segment 1 in theory would be able to accommodate this hydrogen demand. Pipes 4 and 5 in Segment 2, however, exceed their capacity from hour 12 onward. An additional theoretical pipe is added to Segment 2, to lessen the load on Pipes 4 and 5 and reach a mass flow rate profile such that none of the Pipes exceed their capacity at any point.

The added theoretical pipe reported in Figure 41 has a diameter of 36 inches and a pressure limit of 1100psig, the same as Pipe 2. It is responsible for 45% of the total hydrogen mass flow rate, while Pipes 4 and 5 transmit the remaining 55% divided equally.

Figure 41: Pipeline Performance Report with One Additional Pipe, Base Loads, Zones 1 & 2

An analysis comparing the costs of building such an additional pipeline to the costs of reconductoring the overloaded transmission lines will be conducted in Section 7.

5.7.4 Zone 3 – Pipeline Included

Figure 42: Zone 3 Disabled – System Overload Plot

Table 15: Zone 3 Disabled – Pipeline-Included Electrical Performance Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3568	500	67	FALSE	2880	105	2	140
5698	500	66	FALSE	2917	106	2	177

Since only two transmission lines in the lower half of the Palm Springs corridor are affected by the loss of the transmission infrastructure in Zone 3, the pipeline can easily address the overloads.

Figure 43: Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zone 3

Again, as the pipeline system can support the overloads created by the full electrical loads in this case, it is inferred that critical loads can also easily be met using this approach.

5.7.5 Zone 4 - Pipeline Included

Figure 44: Zone 4 Disabled – System Overload Plot

Table 16: Zone 4 Disabled – Pipeline-Included Electrical Performance Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3622	220	8	FALSE	5081	146	9	1601
5744	220	10	TRUE	3256	140	9	936
304	138	3	TRUE	2515	108	4	195
3597	500	76	FALSE	3252	119	6	512
3598	500	76	FALSE	3250	119	6	510
5698	500	66	FALSE	2877	105	2	137

The circuit experiences some electrical overloads downstream of the main pipeline system we are modelling. These overloads are not easily addressed by adding more hydrogen, as this additional hydrogen has no effect on transmission infrastructure that does not run in parallel to the pipeline system. After applying the algorithm to determine the necessary hydrogen flow rate, the circuit is reassessed.

Figure 45: Zone 4 Disabled – Pipeline Hydrogen Applied

Table 17: Zone 4 Disabled – Pipeline Hydrogen Applied, Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3597	500	76	FALSE	3186	116	7	446
3598	500	76	FALSE	3184	116	7	444
3892	500	20	TRUE	4408	107	3	298
3893	500	2	TRUE	2953	108	3	213
3894	500	1	FALSE	5909	108	3	429
3889	500	26	FALSE	2930	107	3	190
3890	500	31	FALSE	2889	105	3	149
3891	500	26	FALSE	2944	107	3	204

Figure 46: Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zone 4

With the inclusion of hydrogen, the overloads have shifted from where they were occurring in Figure 44 to a single transmission branch. These overloads occur because there are loads in the north-western part of the area where there are no generators. The hydrogen compensation algorithm is unable to converge on a solution where there are no overloads in the system, meaning the result of the analysis of this particular case should be considered inconclusive. We suspect that the pipeline system can address these overloads since the performance report (Figure 46) shows the system is below capacity. Most likely, a limitation in the model is preventing convergence.

5.7.6 Zone 5 – Pipeline Included

Figure 47: Zone 5 Disabled – Pipeline-Included System Plot

Table 18: Zone 5 Disabled – Pipeline-Included Electrical Performance Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3880	220	8	TRUE	4143	179	6	1823
3941	220	8	FALSE	4135	178	6	1815
304	138	3	TRUE	2936	127	6	616
3569	220	69	FALSE	2594	112	2	274
3553	220	68	TRUE	2647	114	2	327
3554	220	72	TRUE	2490	107	2	170
3599	220	11	TRUE	2713	117	3	393
3600	220	11	TRUE	2768	119	3	448

Disabling Zone 5 leads to major overloads both in the upper Palm Springs corridor as well as downstream within the basin. By including pipeline hydrogen, all these overloads are addressed, except a new overload is created in the transmission infrastructure in Irvine:

Figure 48: Zone 5 Disabled – Pipeline Hydrogen Applied

Table 19: Zone 5 Disabled – Pipeline-Included Electrical Performance Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3691	220	13	TRUE	2549	110	3	229

Figure 49: Pipeline Performance Report, Full Loads, Zone 5

Since the transmission lines between station 2133 and 381 do not run parallel to the pipeline, and since the only other electrical path to station 381 is cut off when Zone 5 is disabled, these lines become overloaded and cannot be helped by the pipeline infrastructure. The model does not account for generation south of the area, so in the real system it is likely that these overloads would not occur because power can still be transmitted to station 381 from the South.

5.7.7 Conclusions on Hydrogen-Reinforced System Resiliency

When comparing the performance of the existing base system (section 4.2) to this section, the inclusion of the pipeline network significantly increases system resiliency. Most importantly, it achieves this while simultaneously eliminating the need for natural gas based electricity generation in the basin.

Without disabling any zones, the pipeline network can easily support the base system on full electrical loads. Disabling Zones 1 or 2 leads to overloads in the upper and lower Palm Springs corridors respectively, and we have demonstrated that these overloads can be fully alleviated by the pipeline network in sections 5.7.1 and 5.7.2. All loads can be met by the pipeline system if Zone 3 is disabled. Disabling Zones 1 and 2 simultaneously, which is a realistic scenario as they are physically connected, would require the pipeline network to transport hydrogen exceeding its capacity. Specifically, Pipes 4 and 5 would not be able to transport adequate hydrogen to address the system's electrical needs. An additional pipeline identical to Pipes 4 and 5 would need to be built.

Disabling Zones 4 and 5 both lead to a system configuration where the hydrogen compensation algorithm does not converge on a solution where the grid has no electrical overloads. An AC power flow model is highly dynamic, and certain results are difficult to properly diagnose, so it is likely that some limitation in the way the model is set up is preventing this algorithm from converging. However, we are confident that the existing pipeline infrastructure would be capable of addressing the overloads seen when Zones 4 and 5 are disabled, based on the inspection of the performance reports.

6 Performance Under Complete Electrification of End-Uses

The study performed in section 5 was conducted on the assumption that the electrical load profile taken from CAISO historical data accurately represents the complete energy demand in the area. However, these loads are purely electrical and do not account for alternative energy sources, primarily natural gas. To account for natural gas, section 5.5 converted its demand to a hydrogen demand profile, but the flaw with this approach is that it assumes that all natural gas end uses can be retrofitted to use hydrogen. If we instead assume that all natural gas end uses are converted to electrical loads, we can again run an analysis determining whether the pipeline network can support the additional loads.

ResStock and ComStock provide complete electrification load profiles, ranging from low- to high-efficiency, whole-home electrification packages. This is only available at the state level, so we must leverage our other data to increase the resolution and assign new, complete electrification load profiles to the substations. To achieve this, we can determine the hourly ratio between the baseline electrical load and the complete electrification package load, then apply this hourly ratio to each of the substations' current electrical load profiles, like how we determined critical load profiles in section 4.3.

Figure 50: Whole-Home Electrification Package, Min Efficiency – Residential

The upgrade package we are using assumes whole-home electrification at minimum efficiency. This was chosen to determine the system performance in the most conservative efficiency case. As an equivalent package is not provided for the commercial end uses in ComStock, this residential package will be used exclusively to adjust all loads.

Figure 51: Base & Whole-Home Electrification Load Comparison

Figure 51 demonstrates the increased electrical loads because of the whole-home electrification package. However, because we are now accounting for the residential and commercial natural gas end uses in the electrical profiles, we can eliminate the natural gas demand from the pipeline system.

6.1 Resiliency Analysis

Figure 52 shows the increase in hydrogen transmission necessary due to the conversion to whole-home electrification. While natural gas end uses were converted to electrical demand and this decreased the hydrogen profile between hours 2 and 8 (when the electrical grid experiences no overloads), for the rest of the day the resulting electrical overloads demand more hydrogen transmission overall.

Figure 52: Hydrogen Profile Comparisons

Figure 53: Pipeline Performance Report, Electrification Package, Base System

With the added electrical loads from the conversion of natural gas end uses with minimal efficiency, the pipeline network approaches its operational limit in the base system, without disabling any zones.

Since it was established that out of all analyzed cases in section 5.7, the one where both Zones 1 and 2 were disabled simultaneously led to the greatest hydrogen transmission demand, this case will be analyzed to establish how large an additional pipeline would need to be to accommodate this demand without considering storage. This pipeline would represent the highest-demand scenario for hydrogen, and thus require the largest additional pipe.

Figure 54: Pipeline Performance Report, Electrification Package, Zones 1 and 2 Disabled

With Zones 1 and 2 disabled on full electrification loads, the pipeline network fails in both segments. Significant additions to either pipeline infrastructure or electrical transmission infrastructure would be necessary to address this issue.

6.2 Comments on Transportation Electrification

This work has not considered the loads of the transportation sector, nor has it considered the potential electrical loads of a fully electrified transportation sector. The purpose of the work has been to determine the system's ability to provide energy to serve critical loads during extreme events.

To put it into perspective, according to the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) [13], the state of California consumed an energy equivalent of 624TWh of natural gas in 2022. 45% of this natural gas was used for energy generation, and the remainder was for direct natural gas end uses in residential, commercial, and industrial applications. The state consumed an energy equivalent of 434TWh of motor gasoline.

As we have seen, according to the analysis, the system was able to withstand major transmission outages when hydrogen via pipeline distribution is included, but the pipeline infrastructure approached its operational limit in all studied outage scenarios and exceeded it in some. Including an electrical load equivalent to this motor gasoline consumption would be a 70% increase of electrical loads in the model, which the pipeline infrastructure could certainly not handle. These TWh consumption values would imply the necessity to either increase the pipeline infrastructure hydrogen transmission capacity by 70%, or the electrical grid transmission capacity by 70%, to be able to handle the added loads of the transportation sector. This also does not account for the inevitable necessary upgrades to electrical distribution infrastructure. Alternative approaches to deal with the transportation sector would need to be considered, accounting for the electrification of most consumer vehicles.

7 Technoeconomic Analysis

This section serves as a small supplementary analysis of economically relevant aspects to the results of the simulations.

7.1 Base System Resiliency Analysis Results

Without the inclusion of hydrogen via pipeline transmission, we have established that the base system is somewhat resilient to major electrical transmission outages. However, there were a few cases where significant electrical overloads occurred. This subsection of the Technoeconomic Analysis section will analyze the cost of increasing the current carrying capacity of these overloaded transmission lines. Note that there were no major overloads or voltage issues when disabling Zone 1 and 2 transmission lines, so there is no upgrade cost associated with improving the electric and gas transmission system to ensure continued resilience and reliability.

7.1.1 Base System - Zone 3 Disabled Upgrade Cost

When Zone 3 was disabled in the base system, six transmission lines experienced ampacity overloads between 100-120% of their operational limits, lasting several hours. Table 19 takes the relevant data from Table 9 and calculates the total necessary additional current carrying capacity. Based on conductor length and additional required amperage capacity, we can determine base costs of additional conductors using an online retailer known as Pro Wire & Cable [14]. Conductor lengths of 0km are assumed to be 0.5km for pricing purposes. We know these cables are at most 0.5km in length based on the principle of rounding.

Table 20: Base System - Zone 3 Disabled Overload Report

Line	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)	Total Additional Required Capacity (Amps)
5743	0	TRUE	3125	114	4	385	2310
5741	0	FALSE	3125	114	4	385	1155
5742	0	FALSE	3125	114	4	385	1155
3622	8	FALSE	3894	112	3	414	1242
3654	7	TRUE	3108	113	3	368	2208
5744	10	TRUE	2497	108	2	177	1062

For each of the transmission lines, each phase is upgraded with a conductor with the additional required capacity. Using the conductor cost data from [14], a total cost of the upgrade is calculated and shown in Table 20. Single circuits have three phases and double circuits have six phases.

Table 21: Base System – Zone 3 Upgrade Cost

Line	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)	ACSR Conductor Type	ACSR Conductor Cost (/ft)	ACSR Conductor Total Upgrade Cost
5743	0.5	TRUE	385	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$12,111
5741	0.5	FALSE	385	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$6,055
5742	0.5	FALSE	385	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$6,055
3622	8	FALSE	414	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$96,850
3654	7	TRUE	368	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$169,488
5744	10	TRUE	177	Sparate	\$0.40	\$78,740
Total Cost						\$369,299

Thus, to strengthen the system against a scenario where Zone 3 transmission infrastructure is disabled, the conductors alone would cost \$369,299. Since this analysis assumes the upgrade takes advantage of existing transmission towers as well as right-of-way, we make an estimated assumption that installation will cost at least as much as the conductors, leading to a total upgrade

cost of around \$740,000. Even if we assumed the total cost of the upgrade to be 10 times that of the conductors, as a generous estimate, it would still cost under \$4,000,000.

7.1.2 Base System – Zone 4 Disabled Upgrade Cost

Repeating the methodology followed in 7.1.1, we arrive at the Zone 4 upgrade costs shown in Table 20.

Table 22: Base System – Zone 4 Upgrade Cost

Line	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)	ACSR Conductor Type	ACSR Conductor Cost (/ft)	ACSR Conductor Total Upgrade Cost
3597	76	FALSE	458	Merlin	\$2.25	\$1,683,072
3598	76	FALSE	456	Merlin	\$2.25	\$1,683,072
3892	20	TRUE	692	Dove	\$3.10	\$1,220,472
3893	2	TRUE	477	Merlin	\$2.25	\$88,583
3894	1	FALSE	957	Rail	\$4.42	\$43,504
3889	26	FALSE	450	Merlin	\$2.25	\$575,787
3891	26	FALSE	465	Merlin	\$2.25	\$575,787
3890	31	FALSE	405	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$375,295
Total Cost						\$6,245,572

In this case, the cost of the conductors alone is over \$6 million. Making the same generous assumptions about the cost of installation, this upgrade could cost at least \$60 million.

7.1.3 Base System – Zone 5 Disabled Upgrade Cost

Again, we repeat the previous methodology and estimate an upgrade cost. Table 22 shows the conductor costs.

Table 23: Base System – Zone 5 Upgrade Cost

Line	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Percentage of Capacity	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)	ACSR Conductor Type	ACSR Conductor Cost (/ft)	ACSR Conductor Total Upgrade Cost
3876	7	FALSE	118	424	Waxwing	\$1.23	\$84,744
3896	8	TRUE	111	263	Raven	\$0.86	\$135,433
Total Cost							\$220,177

In total, making the same generous assumption that the total cost of the upgrade is 10 times that of the conductors, this leads to a total upgrade cost of \$2,201,770.

7.1.4 Base System – Total Upgrade Cost

To conclude, we have determined a total transmission infrastructure upgrade cost on the order of \$66 million. This assumes that the total cost of installation, including labor and conductors, is 10 times the cost of the conductors alone. With this upgrade, the Southern California electrical transmission grid would be better equipped to deal with significant transmission outages.

7.2 Hydrogen-Augmented System Resiliency Analysis Results

For the few cases where the hydrogen compensation algorithm was unable to converge on a solution where none of the electrical transmission lines were overloaded, it is beneficial to determine the potential costs of upgrading these specific transmission lines as an alternative. To reiterate, in this case, it is assumed that all natural gas power plants in the LA basin are repurposed to use hydrogen, making it a highly renewable case.

7.2.1 Hydrogen-Augmented System – Zone 3

In the hydrogen-augmented system, the pipeline completely addresses all electrical overloads. Thus, no upgrade is necessary.

7.2.2 Hydrogen-Augmented System – Zone 4

Table 24: Zone 4 system details

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)	Additional Required Capacity Per Phase (Amps)
3597	500	76	FALSE	3186	116	7	446
3598	500	76	FALSE	3184	116	7	444
3892	500	20	TRUE	4408	107	3	298
3893	500	2	TRUE	2953	108	3	213
3894	500	1	FALSE	5909	108	3	429
3889	500	26	FALSE	2930	107	3	190
3890	500	31	FALSE	2889	105	3	149
3891	500	26	FALSE	2944	107	3	204

7.3 Hydrogen-Augmented System Additional Pipeline Cost

In one extreme case, part of the pipeline system was unable to handle the hydrogen transmission load. Introducing a new pipeline addressed this problem. Thus, it is important to determine the possible costs of building such a new pipeline, and to compare these costs to that of electrical transmission reconductoring discussed in section 7.2.

8 Conclusion

This report analyzed the resiliency and reliability of the Southern California energy infrastructure, focusing on the potential of hydrogen augmentation through natural gas pipelines to enhance

system performance under stress. Below are the key findings and quantified results from the analysis:

- **Baseline System Resiliency:**
 - The Southern California grid experienced overloads exceeding 120% of operational limits during simulated outages in major transmission zones. These occurred for durations ranging from 2 to 9 hours.
 - Upgrading the electrical infrastructure to handle these overloads would cost an estimated \$66 million, assuming installation costs are ten times the conductor costs.
- **Hydrogen-Augmented System Performance:**
 - Inclusion of hydrogen transmission via pipelines significantly improved system resiliency.
 - Hydrogen pipelines effectively mitigated overloads in Zones 1, 2, and 3 during full load scenarios, without exceeding operational pipeline limits.
 - When Zones 1 and 2 were simultaneously disabled, the existing pipelines were insufficient. Adding one new 36-inch pipeline would enable hydrogen transmission to meet system demand at an estimated capacity increase of 45%.
- **Critical Load Management:**
 - With loads reduced by 20%, most overloads were alleviated, demonstrating the system's ability to prioritize essential services during outages.
 - Under full electrification scenarios, pipeline limits were approached but not exceeded for single-zone outages. However, simultaneous outages of Zones 1 and 2 required additional pipeline infrastructure.
- **Future Outlook:**
 - Transitioning natural gas pipelines to hydrogen transport offers a dual benefit: reducing dependency on fossil fuels and enhancing grid resiliency.
 - However, the complete electrification of end-uses and transportation would increase electrical loads by up to 70%, necessitating significant infrastructure investments in either hydrogen or electrical systems.

This analysis supports the feasibility and economic advantage of using hydrogen infrastructure as a resiliency measure for critical urban energy systems. Further integration of renewable hydrogen and strategic pipeline expansion is recommended to future-proof the Southern California energy grid against increasing demand and extreme events.

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Appendix A – Data Collection for Electric Grid Model

Geospatial Data

Data that describes the location and specifications of important infrastructure was necessary for the development of a model of the electrical and natural gas grids.

California Electrical Transmission Lines

The “California Electric Transmission Lines” dataset provided by the California Energy Commission contains all electrical transmission lines in the state of California and tabulates a set of features for each line. Among these features, those listed below are most significant to our model:

- Line ID number
- Line coordinates (all segments)
- Line voltage rating (in kV)
- Utility that owns the line
- Operational status
- Whether the line is a single or double circuit
- Line length (in miles & feet)

Figure 55 shows a subsection of the dataset in our area of interest: the LA basin and its surrounding regions.

Figure 55: California Electrical Transmission Lines geospatial map

Southern California Edison Distributed Energy Resource Interconnection Map

Substations are key components of the electrical grid. From a modelling standpoint, they are nodes, interconnected by transmission lines. An area’s power generation, as well as load profiles pertaining to the area’s population, can be assigned to these nodes. Southern California Edison has a publicly available geospatial dataset, known as the Distributed Energy Resource Interconnection Map (DERiM). This dataset contains the details describing all substations in the Southern California area, including those owned by other utilities. Like the transmission line data set, this data set provides a list of features for each substation:

- Substation ID
- Substation coordinates
- “System” to which the substation belongs
- DER existing generation (in MW)
- Projected load (in MW)
- Maximum and minimum loads experienced during every hour of every day in a year

Figure 56 shows the plotted substation data taken from DERiM.

Figure 56: DERiM substation geospatial map

Accompanying this geospatial data is a set of comma-separated values describing minimum and maximum experienced loads (in MW) for every substation. Every month is described by a minimum and maximum 24-hour load profile, where the values are based on the minimum and maximum loads experienced at each hour in the entire month. For example, if January 3rd experienced the lowest load at 13:00, while January 20th experienced the highest load at 13:00, they would be selected to describe January's minimum and maximum loads at 13:00 respectively. While this data is not physical as it is an aggregation of data collected over month-long periods rather than describing real individual days, it will be useful in scaling and assigning real, physical data to the nodes.

By combining the transmission line dataset with this substation dataset, it will be possible to build an A/C power flow model that treats the substations as nodes, and the transmission lines as connections between these nodes.

California Power Plants

Alongside geospatial data for the physical infrastructure that constitutes the electrical grid, our model necessitates geospatial data describing the magnitude, location, and type of power generation in the system. The California State Geoportal provides a dataset of all power plants in California, with the following set of features describing each:

- California Energy Commission Plant ID
- Plant Name
- State of retirement (0 or 1)

- Operator Company
- County
- Capacity (in MW)
- Units
- Primary Energy Source (SUN, NG, WIND...)

While this dataset does not contain information regarding generation profiles for any of these plants, the capacity and location data will be useful in scaling and assigning such profiles to substations in their vicinities. Figure 57 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a plot of this dataset, again in our area of interest.

Figure 57: Power Plants

Note that this dataset describes utility-scale generation and does not account for DER resources such as rooftop solar, meaning that the DER data collected from SCE's DERiM is independent from this dataset. Therefore, we can be confident that no generation will be double counted in the model.

Load & Generation Profile Data

California Independent System Operator

To establish a working model that accurately describes the real transmission system in Southern California, real demand and generation data is required. The California Independent System Operator (CAISO) is a powerful resource that provides information on the operation of California’s electric power transmission. In its library, it contains electrical demand and generation data for every day since April 10th, 2018. The generation data is broken down by resource (renewables, natural gas, hydroelectric, etc.) in 5 minute increments, and the renewable generation is further broken down by renewable category (solar, wind, geothermal, etc.). Figure 58 and Figure 59 show this generation data as it is presented on the CAISO website, for August 8th, 2023.

Figure 58: CAISO Overall Generation Profiles

Figure 59: CAISO Renewable Generation Profiles

This data represents the total statewide generation but cannot be separated based on utilities. It is therefore not possible to know how much of the total generation is provided by SCE and LADWP, the utilities of interest in this study.

Load profile data is provided by the California ISO via its Open Access Same-time Information System (OASIS) on an hourly basis, broken down based on utilities. As a result, we can obtain a load profile that adequately represents our area of interest (served by most of SCE and LADWP).

The limitation of this CAISO data is the fact that it is aggregated data (statewide for generation, utility-based for loads). This limitation can be compensated for using certain properties of the geospatial data.

Residential & Commercial Building Stock

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory provides building simulation data in two categories of building stock – residential (ResStock) and commercial (ComStock). Both categories contain data at the state level, which are partitioned into end uses. ‘Upgrade packages’, which simulate the predicted electrical loads of building stock that is partially or entirely electrified, are also available. Monthly data can be downloaded, where the user can obtain a 24-hr profile in units of kWh.

Figure 60: ResStock aggregate load profile

Figure 61: ComStock aggregate load profile

Appendix B - Model Development & Simulation Methodology

This section discusses the development of the AC power flow electrical transmission model.

OpenDSS Electrical Grid Model

OpenDSS is a publicly available AC power flow software developed by the Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI). While it is typically used to conduct analysis on distribution circuits, the software can simulate a transmission system model of our scale and complexity.

Language Format & Requirements for Model

All circuit components in OpenDSS are initialized as objects. The system to be modelled will consist of buses, generators and transformers connected by three-phase transmission lines. In OpenDSS, three-phase transmission lines are initialized as follows:

New Line.{ } Phase=3 Bus1={ }.1.2.3 Bus2={ }.1.2.3 Linecode={ } Length={ } unit=meters

...where each bracketed blank is filled in with a corresponding name, ID, or other relevant number. Transformers, generators, and loads are initialized using similar syntax. OpenDSS is run entirely using these simple lines of code, making it possible to generate an entire script in Python using object-oriented programming.

Python Algorithm

Using the California Electrical Transmission Line and DERiM data sets, the goal is to develop an algorithm that builds a model and writes lines of code to be used by OpenDSS. Since each transmission line in the data set has specified starting and ending point coordinates, and the coordinates for all substations are available, an algorithm can be developed that searches for matches between these coordinate pairs in each data set. In essence, the algorithm will:

1. Create an object for each line in the California Electrical Transmission Line data set, storing the following properties:
 - I. Line ID
 - II. Coordinates for both ends
 - III. Rating (in kV)
 - IV. Length (in meters)

-
2. Create an object for each substation in the DERiM data set, storing the following properties:
 - I. Substation ID
 - II. Coordinates
 3. For each line object, scan through all substations and determine whether the line starting or ending coordinates fall within a specified distance radius of any of the stations. If a substation is found to be close enough to either end of the line, store the station's ID.
 4. Repeat this search for substations on the other end of the line. If a substation is found to be close enough to the end of the line, store the station's ID.
 5. Print a line of code that establishes the connection between the two substations, the length of the line, and its rating.

The resulting lines of code printed by Python can then be directly pasted into OpenDSS to be used for simulation.

Public Use Microdata Areas & Substation Selection

The DERiM resource provided by SCE contains a total of 789 substations. Including all substations in the model would lead to a level of complexity beyond the scope of the project. Additionally, the Python algorithm described in 0 requires much monitoring in the sense that every line of code output by the algorithm is checked for validity, as the transmission line dataset is imperfect and there are many lines that do not start or end in areas where substations are located. Thus, to reduce the complexity of the model, a set of substations was chosen by hand based on location and visual inspection of how many transmission lines have endpoints there. This process led to a total of 24 'primary' substations, adequate to represent the system, plotted in Figure 62.

Figure 62: Key Substations (Buses)

Since each substation in the dataset contains data on local DER capacities, projected loads, and minimum and maximum load profiles, the data pertaining to the remaining 765 ‘secondary’ substations must somehow still be included in the model. To do this, all secondary substations were ‘assigned’ to the nearest selected substation, and their data was aggregated accordingly. This assignment was not done simply based on distance but using Public Use Microdata Area (PUMA) border delineations. As discussed in 0, PUMA delineations divide our area of interest into smaller subsections, which are used by ResStock and ComStock to assign load profile data. By using this approach, we can directly compare ResStock and ComStock load data to the SCE DERiM substation load profile data (or any load profile data scaled using this substation data) based on PUMA delineations.

Figure 63: Map of All Substations in PUMA delineations

Each PUMA delineation was assigned to one of the 24 primary substations based on the proximity of its center point to the nearest primary substation. The secondary substations contained within each delineation were assigned to the primary substations accordingly. Therefore, all numerical data describing the secondary substations was assigned to the 24 primary substations in the model. Equation (3) describes how the loads for all substations were summed and assigned to their corresponding primary substations based on delineations.

$$Load_{total} = Load_{primary} + \sum_{delineation} Load_{secondary} \quad (3)$$

Transmission Infrastructure Model

Using the Python algorithm described in 0, a model of the transmission grid in the area of interest was developed, composed primarily of 220kV and 500kV lines.

Figure 64: Grid Infrastructure

Figure 64 shows that high-voltage lines in the urban environments of the LA Basin are rated at 220kV, while the larger 500kV lines run through longer stretches from the countryside, specifically from areas where renewable generation is sited (Palm Springs, Lancaster...). Note that the “Other Lines” legend entry pertains to transmission lines owned by the LADWP, which are rated differently (287kV, 230kV, 138kV). A large amount of 66kV lines also run through the urban areas alongside these 220kV lines, but they were omitted to avoid excess complexity in the model.

Each substation in the model is assumed to be equipped with a transformer with a winding for each of the possible voltage ratings in the line set, and these transformers are assumed to have practically unlimited capacity. While this removes the ability to evaluate the resiliency and reliability of the transformer infrastructure, it would be difficult to find information regarding the actual capacities of these substations. Estimates on these capacities would be inaccurate and therefore would not lead to meaningful results.

Establishment & Verification of a Base Case

With a model of the transmission grid now fully assembled, validation and testing is necessary to ensure the model is an acceptably accurate representation of the real transmission grid of Southern California. This is essential because there is no publicly available data on the specifications of the circuit components used in the model.

Load Profile Assignment

CAISO, as previously discussed in 0, publishes daily real electrical demand values for all the utilities operating in California. January 1st and August 8th of 2023 were chosen to be run through the model, as they experienced cold and warm weather respectively. The data provided by CAISO, as previously mentioned, is not partitioned beyond the utility level. To divide the CAISO profile among the selected substations, we can utilize the previously aggregated substation data as discussed in 0. The DERiM resource provides the minimum and maximum load profiles for a day in each month for every substation, and these profiles pertaining to all secondary substations were aggregated to each primary substation in the model based on their location in PUMA delineated regions. The average of the minimum and maximum load for each hour was taken to create a new average load profile for each selected substation, then these profiles were summed to create a total load profile for the entire region to compare with the CAISO load profile.

As seen in Figure 65, there is some similarity between the physical CAISO load profile and the calculated aggregated DERiM load profile. While the magnitude of the CAISO profile is significantly higher than that of DERiM for both the cold and hot days, we are not concerned with this discrepancy, as we only aim to split our physical CAISO load profile amongst the substations. By elementwise division of the CAISO load by the DERiM load, a 24-hour set of multiplication factors is calculated. By elementwise multiplication of these factors and load values at each hour, all primary substations are assigned their final load profiles that, when aggregated, equal the CAISO load profile. Figure 66 shows the resulting load profiles for one primary substation which is in the G0606503 PUMA delineation. The profile displays the preservation of the features seen in the CAISO profiles shown in Figure 65.

Figure 65: CAISO load profile compared with DERiM aggregated load profile

Figure 66: Final Load Profiles for PUMA region G0606503

Generation Profile Assignment

Assigning generation to the substations requires a similar approach as taken for the load profiles. CAISO generation profiles (as seen in 0) are aggregated for the whole state, and thus need to be scaled down accordingly, before being divided among the substations.

To assign generation to each substation, the California Power Plant geospatial dataset collected from the Geoportal, as discussed in 0, becomes useful. This dataset contains all generation power plants in the state, their type of generation, and their power output in MW. With

the same approach as taken in assigning load profiles to the substations in 0, each substation is assigned a set of power plants based on their proximity.

Figure 67 shows all power generation plants that are included in the model and assigned to their nearest substations. With a generation capacity value for every type of generation attached to each substation, the generation profiles can be divided amongst the substations accordingly. For example, if there is a total of 20GW of natural gas generation in the region, and a substation has a natural gas generation capacity value of 2GW, it will be responsible for 10% of the total natural gas generation profile. The total generation capacity for each generation type was found and tabulated. The generation profiles provided by CAISO in 0 are not partitioned by utility, but the load profiles provided by CAISO OASIS are. By taking the ratio between the SCE + LADWP loads and the statewide loads at each hour, we arrive at an array of ratios at each hour that can be multiplied elementwise by the generation profiles to obtain an approximation of the local generation profiles.

Figure 67: Generation Plant Map

$$\vec{\alpha} = (\overline{Load}_{SCE} + \overline{Load}_{LADWP}) \oslash \overline{Load}_{CA} \quad (4)$$

$$\overline{Gen}_{SCE+LADWP} = \vec{\alpha} \odot \overline{Gen}_{CA} \quad (7)$$

In observation of Figure 68, notice that utility solar, the solar generation provided by the CAISO profile, has been scaled such that its maximum output does not exceed the solar generation capacity. Wind, hydroelectric, geothermal and imported profiles are untouched. Rooftop solar generation is the generation provided by the DERiM resource, which provides existing customer-side solar generation capacity for each substation. This profile was constructed using these capacity numbers coupled with a solar generation profile for the Los Angeles area in August, downloaded from the NREL PVWatts tool. Two High-Voltage DC transmission lines known as Path 27 and Path 65 are responsible for a significant amount of imported power into the basin. With capacities of 2.4GW and 3.1GW respectively, they are more than capable of transmitting the importation profile seen in Figure 68, and thus will be inserted into the model for the purpose of supplying all importation to the system. Note that they are single-phase HVDC lines that will be treated as three-phase AC lines with the same capacity to avoid adding complexity to the model. The imports profile was adjusted such that there is constant importation of power at 50% of the maximum capacity of these two HVDC lines, a conservative estimate for simplicity and to avoid needing to ramp up the natural gas duty cycle to unreasonable levels. Figure 69 displays this adjusted import generation profile.

Figure 68: August 8th Load & Generation Profiles

Figure 69: Adjusted Load & Generation Profiles

With a total generation profile for each type of generation established for the area covered by the model, this generation can be divided among the substations using the generation capacity values assigned to each substation.

On Energy Storage

This model of a base case will not include battery energy storage due to the sizing and placement of the existing storage in the state. According to the California Energy Storage System Survey ([15]), the state has a total energy storage capacity of 10.383GW. Most of this capacity is owned by utility companies. Because the generation profiles were taken directly from CAISO, the dynamics of storage and dispatch are already integrated. As such, for the base case, which aims only to simulate a real day, formally including battery energy storage as a generation profile was deemed unnecessary.

Transmission Line Parameters

The parameters governing transmission line dynamics in OpenDSS, namely operating ampacity, resistance, capacitance and resistance, are all defined in a 'linecode'. A linecode needs to be defined for each type of transmission line included in the model – 500kV, 220kV and other high-voltage lines are built using differently sized conductors and thus will not have the same electrical properties. Southern California Edison declined to provide details on the conductors used in their transmission lines, and therefore some estimates must be made to proceed.

To make an initial estimate on the physical parameters of the transmission lines in the circuit, transmission line conductor data was necessary. Aluminum Conductor, Steel Reinforced (ACSR) conductors are the standard conductors used in transmission line infrastructure. In the Transmission Line Reference Book [16] published by EPRI, a table containing critical information

on ACSR conductors is provided. From this table, which contains dozens of different conductors, a set of conductors were selected to be assigned to the different transmission lines in the model.

These conductors were chosen based on the assumption that higher-voltage lines will have higher current-carrying capacities, though this is not verifiable. The values shown in the table apply to individual conductors, of which there are three in a three-phase transmission line. Some transmission lines carry double circuits, meaning there are two separate three-phase circuits with a conductor each, a total of six conductors. The transmission line dataset discussed in 0 accounts for this, as it states for every line in the dataset whether that line is a single or double circuit. Double-circuit transmission lines will be treated as two identical single-circuit transmission lines in parallel. OpenDSS linecode requires capacitance specifications which are not included in the table taken from [16]. Instead, physical measurements of capacitance for a 220kV line were taken from [17], then applied to the other voltages simply using numerical ratios between the voltages to increase or decrease the capacitance. With this conductor data and the knowledge of the number of conductors in every transmission line, we have a first working model of the electrical transmission system and can begin to adjust parameters according to whether the model behaves as expected.

Upon resolving a circuit, OpenDSS provides analytics that allow the user to determine whether the circuit is operating correctly. Among these analytics, the per-unit (pu) voltage system and the ampacity overload spreadsheet are the most indicative of issues. The p.u. voltage system shows whether the circuit components are operating at their specified voltages, without significant under- or over-voltages. Ideally, the p.u. voltage is equal to 1 throughout the entire circuit, although in practice the agreed-upon acceptable range is from 0.95 to 1.05, a 5% error. Thus, if a transmission line is rated to operate at 500kV, but drops to below 475kV, this is considered an undervoltage.

Over- and under-voltages are caused by significant events. A lightning strike hitting a transformer would be one example of a cause for an over-voltage, while an under-voltage can occur when the demand for power in a circuit exceeds the rated power of a component in the circuit, leading to a voltage drop. In the base case circuit, it is assumed that such events do not occur, and that the circuit is fully capable of transmitting the power generated and demanded. Thus, over- and under-voltages indicate that transmission line parameters are not properly specified.

Ampacity overloads occur when lines in the circuit are required to transmit currents that exceed their operating capacities. Overloads lead to the degradation of the transmission infrastructure and should be avoided. Lines operating at over 105% of their capacity will be overloaded. OpenDSS provides an overload report on the circuit, showing the overloaded lines, their ampacities, and the hours in which these overloads occurred. Using these metrics to describe the system's performance, a first run of the model can be conducted and evaluated.

The chosen parameters for the transmission lines do not lead to what would be considered an acceptable voltage profile in practice. The two red lines in Figure 70 mark the acceptable p.u. voltage range (0.95-1.05), and the blue lines denote the transmission lines in the model, starting at Palm Springs on the left where the source bus is situated (note that the lines move from left to right on the graph, while on the map they are really moving from East to West). From inspection, Figure 70 shows a significant voltage drop across the power lines.

Table 26 shows a minimum undervoltage of 0.63 pu, with a total of 19 undervoltage buses. This is far below the acceptable minimum.

Figure 70: Base Case Voltage Profile

Figure 71: Base Case Overload Plot

Table 25: Base Case Voltage Report

Maximum Over-voltage	Maximum Hour	Number of Over-voltages at Max Hour	Minimum Under-voltage	Minimum Hour	Number of Under-voltages at Min Hour
1.006711	5	0	0.619941	19	249

Table 26: Base Case Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)
3564	500	25	FALSE	1486	108	2
3694	220	10	TRUE	1740	150	3
3622	220	8	FALSE	2941	254	12
3685	220	16	TRUE	2116	182	3
3664	220	16	TRUE	2099	181	3
3892	500	20	TRUE	2671	195	1
3893	500	2	TRUE	1782	130	1
3894	500	1	FALSE	3564	260	1
3895	500	12	FALSE	2190	160	2
3703	220	9	TRUE	3112	268	3
3896	220	8	TRUE	1459	126	2
3876	220	7	FALSE	1550	134	2
297	500	10	FALSE	1510	110	1
298	500	11	FALSE	1500	109	1
3555	220	25	TRUE	1425	123	3
3556	220	25	TRUE	1408	121	3
3873	220	24	FALSE	1455	125	3
3903	220	6	TRUE	1530	132	3
3699	220	6	TRUE	1516	131	3
3569	220	69	FALSE	1420	122	4
3553	220	68	TRUE	1450	125	4
3889	500	26	FALSE	1775	130	1
3890	500	31	FALSE	1776	130	1
3891	500	26	FALSE	1783	130	1
3653	500	65	FALSE	3440	251	3
3916	220	37	TRUE	1414	122	1
3696	220	5	TRUE	1376	119	3
3568	500	67	FALSE	1785	130	6
5698	500	66	FALSE	1809	132	6
3554	220	72	TRUE	1362	117	3
3691	220	13	TRUE	1339	115	2
3697	220	5	TRUE	1335	115	2
3860	220	1	TRUE	1278	110	1

Table 27: Base Case Voltage Report

Maximum Over-voltage	Maximum Hour	Number of Over-voltages at Max Hour	Minimum Under-voltage	Minimum Hour	Number of Under-voltages at Min Hour
1.006711	5	0	0.619941	19	249

The parameter that has the most impact on this voltage drop was determined through trial and error to be the reactance in the linecodes. Despite the assumption that the conductor reactance specifications provided by the ACSR data table in [16] are accurate, it was found that the model could only produce an acceptable voltage profile when the reactance was reduced by an order of magnitude. While no source in the literature uses line reactance values below those in the ACSR table, there is no other simple way to produce acceptable voltage profiles in the model than by reducing the reactance.

An explanation for this discrepancy between the real system and the model is the lack of reactive power compensation in the model. According to a review of Reactive Power Compensation published in IEEE [18], reactive power compensation is used to “[increase] the maximum active power that can be transmitted. It also helps to maintain a substantially flat voltage profile at all levels of power transmission” ([18], page 1). One method used to achieve reactive power compensation is known as ‘Series Compensation’, where capacitors are installed in series to “decrease the equivalent reactance of a power line at a rated frequency” ([18], page 2 section B). Thus, the direct manual reduction of reactance leads to the same result as Series Compensation (being reduced reactance along the power lines). Ultimately, the need for reactive power compensation in the real transmission circuit arises from the fact that the transmission line reactance is a fixed physical parameter. It is therefore essential as a physical way to reduce equivalent reactance and avoid voltage drops. However, in the simulated model of the system, the line reactance is not fixed, and can be manipulated directly, achieving the same result as, and eliminating the need for, reactive power compensation.

Adjusting the transmission line reactance parameters across all linecodes by an order of magnitude, OpenDSS yields the following results. While Figure 72 shows that the order of magnitude reduction in the line reactance has produced an acceptable voltage profile, and Figure 73 shows fewer overloaded transmission lines than Figure 71, there are still undervoltages and many overloaded lines in the circuit. Table 28: Adjusted Reactance Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)
3564	500	25	FALSE	2566	187	3
3694	220	10	TRUE	2341	202	6
3622	220	8	FALSE	4433	382	11
3685	220	16	TRUE	2346	202	4
3664	220	16	TRUE	2327	201	4
3892	500	20	TRUE	2836	207	3
3893	500	2	TRUE	1891	138	3
3894	500	1	FALSE	3783	276	3
3895	500	12	FALSE	2681	196	4
3703	220	9	TRUE	2936	253	3
297	500	10	FALSE	1649	120	4
298	500	11	FALSE	1637	119	4
3889	500	26	FALSE	1877	137	3
3890	500	31	FALSE	1878	137	3
3891	500	26	FALSE	1886	138	3
3653	500	65	FALSE	2168	158	4
3912	220	14	TRUE	1306	113	3
3568	500	67	FALSE	1873	137	3
5698	500	66	FALSE	1897	138	3
3691	220	13	TRUE	1676	144	4
3903	220	6	TRUE	1452	125	2
3699	220	6	TRUE	1439	124	2
3687	220	9	TRUE	1459	126	2
3688	220	9	TRUE	1454	125	2
3690	69	9	TRUE	1459	126	2
3860	220	1	TRUE	1495	129	2
3742	220	6	TRUE	1246	107	2
3916	220	37	TRUE	1269	109	2

shows the set of transmission lines in the circuit that experience overloads at least once in the 24 hour simulation. Lines for which the ‘Double Circuit’ entry is TRUE should be counted twice, as they have identical lines running in parallel that experience the same overload. Note that these lines are experiencing amperages between 100% and 500% of normal operating capacity. Before these overloads can be addressed, first the loads and generation must be completely balanced in the circuit.

Figure 72: Adjusted Reactance Voltage Profile

Figure 73: Adjusted Reactance Overload Plot

Table 28: Adjusted Reactance Voltage Report

Maximum Over-voltage	Maximum Hour	Number of Over-voltages	Minimum Under-voltage	Minimum Hour	Number of Under-
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	at Max Hour			voltages at Min Hour		
1.048468	1	0	0.93804	17	18	

Table 29: Adjusted Reactance Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)
3564	500	25	FALSE	2566	187	3
3694	220	10	TRUE	2341	202	6
3622	220	8	FALSE	4433	382	11
3685	220	16	TRUE	2346	202	4
3664	220	16	TRUE	2327	201	4
3892	500	20	TRUE	2836	207	3
3893	500	2	TRUE	1891	138	3
3894	500	1	FALSE	3783	276	3
3895	500	12	FALSE	2681	196	4
3703	220	9	TRUE	2936	253	3
297	500	10	FALSE	1649	120	4
298	500	11	FALSE	1637	119	4
3889	500	26	FALSE	1877	137	3
3890	500	31	FALSE	1878	137	3
3891	500	26	FALSE	1886	138	3
3653	500	65	FALSE	2168	158	4
3912	220	14	TRUE	1306	113	3
3568	500	67	FALSE	1873	137	3
5698	500	66	FALSE	1897	138	3
3691	220	13	TRUE	1676	144	4
3903	220	6	TRUE	1452	125	2
3699	220	6	TRUE	1439	124	2
3687	220	9	TRUE	1459	126	2
3688	220	9	TRUE	1454	125	2
3690	69	9	TRUE	1459	126	2
3860	220	1	TRUE	1495	129	2
3742	220	6	TRUE	1246	107	2
3916	220	37	TRUE	1269	109	2

Net Load Adjustment

There is a mismatch between the loads and generation in the circuit, since the sum of all generation profiles in 0 does not equal the total load profile. This mismatch is compensated for by the source bus, an OpenDSS component that can provide active and reactive power generation to meet loads. The source bus is placed at substation 339 in Palm Springs in the model, meaning that a net load in the circuit must be compensated for by generation that is forced to run through only two transmission paths to stations 336 and 347, seen in Figure 73. This leads to overloads in these

paths that are not physical. Since it is crucial to the analysis to correctly specify the parameters of these key transmission lines in Palm Springs, it must be addressed.

Figure 74 shows the net active power supplied by the source bus in Palm Springs, peaking at over 4GW. This is a significant amount of generation being forced through the Palm Springs corridor. To eliminate the source bus power contribution to the circuit, the natural gas generation needs to be ramped up to meet the net loads. This can be achieved by taking the net load profile provided by OpenDSS and adding its values to the natural gas generation profile, then rerunning the model. To reduce the net load profile to zero, this must be done for multiple iterations.

Figure 74: Initial OpenDSS Net Load

Figure 75 and Figure 76 show the progression of the computed net loads compensated for by OpenDSS and the resulting increased natural gas generation profiles intended to meet these net loads. With each iteration, the net load quickly approaches 0. The fourth iteration natural gas profile produces a net load in the 100s of kW, which is negligible in the system. As a form of validation, peak natural gas generation is around 13GW, which is below the computed 18GW natural gas capacity in the area, making this profile realistic and producible in the real system.

Figure 75: Iterations of net load profiles

Figure 76: Iterations of Natural Gas Duty Cycle

OpenDSS provides a net reactive power load. Reactive power until now has not been considered in the generation profiles, but it plays an important role because it can still contribute to overloads, and the source bus should therefore also be producing net zero reactive power to have no influence on the base circuit. Natural gas power plants are able to produce reactive power when necessary. Thus, the reactive power requirement is compensated for by using the natural gas

generators, applying the same iterative method. Figure 77 shows the final active and reactive natural gas profiles inserted into the model to achieve a system where loads and generation are perfectly balanced. In total, the natural gas plants are providing around 13GW of active and 4GW of reactive power to the circuit at their peak, which is below the 18GW capacity identified earlier.

Figure 77: Final Natural Gas Profiles

Figure 78: Zero Net Load Overload Plot

Table 30: Zero Net Load Overload Report

Line	Voltage (kV)	Length (km)	Double Circuit	Highest Amperage (Per Phase)	Percentage of Capacity	Time Spent Overloaded (Hours)
3564	500	25	FALSE	2928	214	7
3694	220	10	TRUE	2690	232	6
3622	220	8	FALSE	3390	292	10
3685	220	16	TRUE	2739	236	5
3664	220	16	TRUE	2717	234	5
3892	500	20	TRUE	3285	240	6
3893	500	2	TRUE	2189	160	6
3894	500	1	FALSE	4381	320	6
3895	500	12	FALSE	2868	209	6
3703	220	9	TRUE	3534	305	5
297	500	10	FALSE	1850	135	7
298	500	11	FALSE	1837	134	7
3889	500	26	FALSE	2162	158	6
3890	500	31	FALSE	2163	158	6
3891	500	26	FALSE	2172	159	6
3653	500	65	FALSE	2699	197	5
3691	220	13	TRUE	1994	172	5
3903	220	6	TRUE	1752	151	4
3699	220	6	TRUE	1736	150	4
3687	220	9	TRUE	1713	148	4
3688	220	9	TRUE	1708	147	4
3690	69	9	TRUE	1713	148	4
3860	220	1	TRUE	1742	150	4
3916	220	37	TRUE	1556	134	3
3742	220	6	TRUE	1331	115	4
3876	220	7	FALSE	1243	107	3
3660	220	10	TRUE	1308	113	3
3661	220	10	TRUE	1311	113	3
3696	220	5	TRUE	1258	108	2
3697	220	5	TRUE	1220	105	2
3712	220	9	TRUE	1170	101	1
3896	220	8	TRUE	1170	101	1

After balancing the loads and generation to achieve a net zero input from the source bus, at least one line that was overloaded in the Palm Springs corridor is no longer overloaded. From here, all overloads in the system can be addressed using a component known as a bundled conductor.

Bundled conductors are composed of two or more conductors in parallel, thereby increasing current-carrying capacity and reducing resistance and reactance. While no scholarly

source citing the prevalence of bundled conductors could be found, the CPUC corroborates the statement that the phases of lines rated above 200kV “can consist of multiple (bundled) conductors” [19]. Furthermore, ‘double’ conductors (bundles containing two conductors) have been discussed in literature as early as 1932 [20]. Most importantly, the poor performance of the current model suggests the existence of bundled conductors in the real system.

To address the current overloads, all overloaded lines will be assigned new linecodes based on how much they are transmitting over their operating capacity. Double, triple and quadruple conductor bundles will have double, triple and quadruple current carrying capacities respectively. Additionally, their resistances will be divided by two, three and four respectively based on the parallel resistor law:

$$\frac{1}{R_{TOT}} = \sum \frac{1}{R_i} \quad (5)$$

Reactance and capacitance may not be affected as simply as resistance, as suggested by [20], which states double conductors lead to merely a 20% decrease in reactance and a 20% increase in capacitance. It will be assumed that double conductors abide by these changes, and that triple and quadruple conductors have the same reactance and capacitance as double conductors, for simplicity.

As a first adjustment to the system, it will be assumed that all lines rated 220kV and over will be equipped with double conductors at minimum. Overloads that persist after this adjustment will be addressed as follows:

- Lines equipped with single conductors that experience overloads between 100-200% will be assigned double conductors.
- Lines equipped with double conductors that experience overloads between 100-150% will be assigned triple conductors.
- Lines equipped with double conductors that experience overloads exceeding 150% will be assigned quadruple conductors.

After making this adjustment, the system experiences no overloads and no voltage anomalies, confirmed by Figure 79. Thus, with the system fully meeting electrical loads without current overloads anywhere in the circuit, we have established a base case representative of the real electrical transmission system and can now proceed with analyzing its performance.

Figure 79: Final Base Case Overload Plot